

This work was carried out in whole or in part within the framework of the NOMATEN Centre of Excellence, supported from the European Union Horizon 2020 research and innovation program (Grant Agreement No. 857470) and from the European Regional Development Fund via the Foundation for Polish Science International Research Agenda PLUS program (Grant No. MAB PLUS/2018/8), and the Ministry of Science and Higher Education's initiative "Support for the Activities of Centers of Excellence Established in Poland under the Horizon 2020 Program" (agreement no. MEiN/2023/DIR/3795).

The version of record of this article, first published in Journal of Nuclear Materials, Volume 617, November 2025, 156131, on 29 August 2025, is available online at Publisher's website:
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnucmat.2025.156131>

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Mechanical properties, 475 °C embrittlement and irradiation resistance of FeCrAl-Y₂O₃ ODS alloy with Ti and V alloying additions

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HIGHLIGHTS

- The results show a significant impact of minor vanadium addition on properties.
- The alloys present high ultimate tensile strength at RT – up to 993±10 MPa.
- High-temperature tensile strength is also promising – at 600 °C, it is 541±18 MPa.
- The addition of vanadium limits the effects of 475 °C embrittlement.
- The vanadium addition increases ion irradiation resistance.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Oxide dispersion strengthened alloy
FeCrAl ODS
Powder metallurgy
Mechanical strength
475 °C embrittlement
Ion irradiation resistance

ABSTRACT

FeCrAl-based ODS alloys are promising for Generation IV nuclear reactor components since they present remarkable properties, such as high mechanical strength and good irradiation resistance. However, there is still relatively little information on the impact of minor alloying elements, e.g., Ti or V, and manufacturing conditions on the properties of these alloys. In this paper, two FeCrAl-based alloys with the minor addition of Y₂O₃, Ti, and V were studied. The investigation focuses on the mechanical properties at high temperatures (up to 800 °C), resistance to so-called “475 °C embrittlement” (α and α' phase separation), and irradiation resistance. The conducted tensile tests show promising mechanical properties at room temperature, i.e., the yield strength is 893 ± 23 MPa, and the ultimate tensile strength is 993 ± 10 MPa. The tensile tests at high temperatures also confirm good properties, e.g., at 600 °C the yield strength is 490 ± 8 MPa, the ultimate tensile strength is 526 ± 14 MPa, while the total elongation is 17 ± 4 %. The results reveal that adding vanadium increases the strength of the FeCrAl ODS alloys. The conducted annealing at 475 °C for 1000 h shows limited hardening and almost no change in elongation of the alloy with the addition of vanadium. The performed ion irradiation experiments show good irradiation resistance of both tested alloys, manifesting by limited hardening and stable oxide precipitates. The results confirm the promising properties of studied materials for application in the nuclear industry, particularly

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnucmat.2025.156131>

Received 28 February 2025; Received in revised form 11 July 2025; Accepted 29 August 2025

Available online 29 August 2025

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in Generation IV reactors. Moreover, the results show the possibility of tuning properties by adding alloying elements, such as vanadium.

1. Introduction

The Generation IV nuclear reactor design concept assumes significantly higher operation temperatures, pressure, and irradiation damage than existing nuclear reactors [1]. Oxide dispersion-strengthened (ODS) alloys are promising materials because they exhibit good high-temperature strength, creep resistance, high irradiation resistance, and corrosion resistance [1–3]. The primary source of these outstanding properties is fine grain size matrix phase and nanometric oxide precipitates, which act as sinks for defects and block movements of dislocations, improving irradiation resistance and mechanical strength [3,4]. Most ODS alloys are produced by powder metallurgy, such as hot extrusion (HE) and hot isostatic pressing (HIP) techniques, due to the possibility of fabrication of nanometric oxides homogeneously distributed in the matrix [5]. However, recent studies showed promising properties of alloys consolidated by spark plasma sintering (SPS) in a significantly shorter time [6–8]. Many different stoichiometric oxides are found in various ODS alloys, e.g., Y_2O_3 [3,7,9,10], $Y_2Zr_2O_7$ [3], $Y_4Zr_3O_{12}$ [3,8,11,12], Y_2TiO_5 [3,13], hexagonal $YAlO_3$ (known as YAH) [3], orthorhombic $YAlO_3$ (known as YAP) [3,8,14], $Y_4Al_2O_9$ (YAM) [9, 11,12,15–17], $Y_3Al_5O_{12}$ (YAG) [9,15,16,18], $Y_2Ti_2O_7$ [19,20], and $Y_3Al_5O_{12}$ [19], but also non-stoichiometric oxides such as Y-Ti-O enriched clusters tend to form in the alloys' matrix [20]. ODS materials have different fine-grain matrices, such as austenitic, ferritic-martensitic, and ferritic.

FeCrAl-based ODS alloys with a ferritic matrix seem highly promising as accident-tolerant fuel (ATF) claddings [3,4,21]. The presence of Cr significantly improves corrosion resistance [22]. The content of Al in the matrix substantially improves the corrosion and oxidation resistance of ODS alloys by forming a dense protective layer on the surface [23–26]. However, the presence of Al could lead to the formation of relatively large aluminum oxides, which are not beneficial in terms of mechanical properties [11,27]. Y_2O_3 oxide is usually added to the mixture of powders, and then during powder metallurgy processing, reacts with alloying elements, forming complex oxides. One of the alloying elements beneficial in oxide formation in ODS alloys is Ti [7,20, 28]. Simultaneously, adding vanadium to ODS alloys can prevent grain growth and increase hardness by a solid solution strengthening mechanism [19] and promote nanometric precipitate formation [29,30].

Most studies focus on detailed microstructural characterization and mechanical properties at room temperatures of ODS alloys. In contrast, studies investigating high-temperature mechanical properties are less common. Oksiuta et al. [31] studied Fe-14Cr-2W-0.3Ti-0.3Y $_2$ O $_3$ ODS alloy consolidated by HIP. The authors found a significant impact on processing conditions on mechanical properties. The most promising conditions show a yield strength of 866 ± 23 MPa and an elongation of 16.2 ± 1.0 % at room temperature and a yield strength of 475 ± 10 MPa with an elongation of 18.8 ± 1.0 % at 600 °C. Cao et al. [12] investigated Fe-5Cr-4.5Al-0.6Zr prepared by mechanical alloying and HIP and found the ultimate tensile strength of 875 MPa at room temperature and 234 MPa at 700 °C. These results show the exceptional strength of ODS; however, the elongation is quite limited. According to investigations by Yan et al. [4], the elongation in a tensile test of an ODS alloy is more significant when the average size of precipitates is smaller.

However, one of the most common problems related to FeCrAl ODS alloys applied in high-temperature operation is embrittlement after prolonged exposure at temperatures near 475 °C. It is associated with the separation of the bcc matrix into iron-rich α and chromium-rich α' phases [32]. Alloys with a lower content of Cr present better resistance to 475 °C embrittlement. The chromium content between 10 and 12 wt. % seems optimal to have sufficient oxidation resistance while usually

preventing harmful embrittlement [33–35]. Moreover, it appears that aluminum content (> 2 at. %) can suppress or limit α' phase formation [33]; however, other researchers show that for alloys with lower Cr content, Al can promote embrittlement [36]. Nevertheless, according to Han et al. [36], ODS alloys present better 475 °C embrittlement resistance than alloys with the same composition without complex oxide precipitates.

ODS alloys reveal exceptional irradiation resistance due to nanometric oxide precipitates, which can act as sinks for defects, decreasing the number of irradiation-induced defects [37]. Ion-irradiation has been frequently used to evaluate irradiation resistance [37,38]. TEM investigations coupled with nanoindentation measurements can determine the material response to irradiation. Many studies assess the behavior of nanometric oxides in ODS alloys under irradiation conditions. The variety of irradiation conditions (ions, doses, temperatures) makes it challenging to evaluate the behavior of oxide precipitates [39]. In the literature, many articles show significantly different results, such as stable oxide precipitates, dissolution of precipitates, or growth of precipitates under irradiation [39–42]. Some differences between the stability of various oxides were noticed [42]. Therefore, more investigations are needed to understand the behavior of nanometric oxides. Moreover, the irradiation of FeCrAl alloys could result in the formation of the Cr-rich α' phase, which increases the hardness of the alloy and is very brittle [43].

The purpose of the study is to continue the evaluation of prepared FeCrAl- Y_2O_3 ODS alloys with the additions of Ti and V for application in the nuclear industry [7,44]. The paper assesses mechanical properties by performing tensile tests at room temperature and in situ at high temperatures up to 800 °C. Moreover, the behavior of the FeCrAl ODS under prolonged annealing at 475 °C is investigated. In addition, the irradiation resistance of the produced alloys is studied by performing ion-irradiation experiments. Therefore, in this paper, we analyze the critical properties of FeCrAl ODS alloys for application in Generation IV nuclear reactors.

2. Materials and methods

Two compositions of FeCrAl-based ODS alloys with Ti, V, and Y_2O_3 additions, listed in Table 1, were studied. Mechanical alloying (MA) was performed from pure elements in a Retsch PM100 planetary ball mill in a milling jar made of martensitic stainless steel. MA was performed at 250 rotations per minute (rpm) for 50 h in an argon atmosphere. A balls-to-powder ratio was 5:1. The total powder weight obtained in one batch was approximately 50 g. Powders from MA were consolidated using the spark plasma sintering (SPS) technique in a device produced by the Lukaszewicz Institute of Microelectronics and Photonics, Poland. The process was carried out in a graphite round die ($\Phi = 25$ mm), and the height of the sample was about 9 mm. The consolidation was performed in 10 min at 1050 °C under uniaxial pressure of 40 MPa. After sintering, the homogenization annealing was performed at 1020 °C for 30 minutes under argon, followed by cooling in air. More details on the preparation of the samples can be found in our previous papers [7,44]. The measurements of oxygen and carbon contents were performed in our

Table 1
Chemical composition (wt. %) of studied FeCrAl ODS alloys.

Sample	Chemical composition (wt. %)					
	Fe	Cr	Al	Y_2O_3	Ti	V
ODS-1-Ti	Balance	12.0	5.0	0.3	1.0	-
ODS-2-TiV	Balance	12.0	5.0	0.3	1.0	0.5

previous paper [7]. The content of oxygen is 0.44 wt. % and 0.42 wt. % in the ODS-1-Ti and the ODS-2-TiV sample, respectively. The content of carbon was determined at 0.030 wt. % and 0.078 wt. % in the ODS-1-Ti and ODS-2-TiV samples, respectively. Contamination elements not listed in Table 1 can have a significant impact on microstructure and properties. The content of S and P was measured by the Optical Emission Spectroscopy (OES) technique using a Bruker Q4 Tasman Series 2 device. The measured content of S is 0.005 wt. % in both studied samples. The P content is 0.01 wt. % in both samples.

One batch of samples was submitted to the 475 °C annealing for 1000 h in the air, followed by slow cooling in the furnace to evaluate the resistance of produced alloys to the so-called “475 °C embrittlement”. Another batch of samples was submitted to ion irradiation to mimic neutron damage in a nuclear reactor. The surface of the samples before ion irradiation was electropolished to obtain a stress-free surface. A mask covered one-half of each sample during irradiation to directly compare the pristine and irradiated areas. The macroscopic image of the virgin and irradiated areas is shown in Fig. S1 (please refer to *Supplementary materials*). The ion implantation was performed with Fe²⁺ ions (self-ion irradiation) with an energy of 10 MeV at 300 °C. The temperature was selected to simulate irradiation at conditions similar to an operating nuclear reactor [43]. ODS-1-Ti alloy was implanted to the dose of 1 displacement per atom (dpa) (fluence 1×10^{15} ions/cm²), while the ODS-2-TiV alloy was implanted up to 5 dpa (fluence 5×10^{15} ions/cm²). To help design experiments of irradiation resistance, the Fe ions concentration in irradiated samples and the damage profile (dpa) were calculated using the Stopping and Range of Ions in Matter software, abbreviated as SRIM, using full cascade mode [45]. SRIM software enables computing radiation damage [46], and it is frequently used for different materials, including ODS alloys [6,47–49]. The displacement energy was based on the literature data [50]. Density inserted into SRIM software was measured using the Archimedes method and can be found in authors previous publication [44], i.e., 7.20 g/cm³ for ODS-1-Ti and 7.19 g/cm³ for ODS-2-TiV. The profiles of damage and concentration of Fe ions are shown in Fig. 1. The peak of the Fe ions range was found at a depth of 2.08 μm, while the peak damage was found at a depth of 1.92 μm.

Microstructural investigations of samples were performed using a Helios 5 UX scanning electron microscope (SEM) by ThermoFisher Scientific in various modes, i.e., secondary electron imaging, backscattered electron imaging, energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS), and electron backscatter diffraction (EBSD). All SEM images and EBSD maps of microstructure were taken from the central part of the cross-section of the sintered samples. The lamella for TEM observations in as-sintered conditions, after 475 °C annealing for 1000 h, and after ion irradiation

were prepared using the Focused Ion Beam (FIB) technique. The final thinning was done using a 2 kV beam to limit the damage created by impacting Ga⁺ ions. The transmission electron microscopy (TEM) investigations were carried out using a Jeol JEM-F200 TEM operating at an accelerating voltage of 200 kV. The volume fraction of nanometric precipitates and their size distribution were measured using ImageJ software from TEM images covering at least the area of 5 μm². The dislocation density measurements were performed using the line intercept method based on TEM images. The area of measurements consisted of six grains for each sample, covering an area of approximately 1.5 μm². The thickness of the lamella was determined based on convergent beam electron diffraction (CBED) patterns [51].

The XRD investigations were carried out using a Bruker D8 Advance diffractometer to evaluate ion-irradiation-induced damage. The X-ray tube had a Cu anode and was powered by 40 kV and 40 mA ($\lambda_{\text{CuK}\alpha 1} = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$). The measurement range covered $2\theta = 35^\circ \div 140^\circ$ since there are no diffraction peaks spotted below $2\theta = 35^\circ$ and above 140° . Two measurements were performed for each sample: the Bragg-Brentano (BB) para-focusing geometry was used for the virgin (non-implanted) areas, and the grazing incidence (GI) geometry was used for the ion-implanted regions. The grazing incidence beam geometry was chosen to maximize the signal originating from the implantation-affected volume. The incidence angle was set to $\omega = 5^\circ$. Calculated effective penetration depth of CuK α X-rays assuming sample density of 7.20 g/cm³, incident beam angle $\omega = 5^\circ$ and 2θ diffraction angle of 95° (i.e., it is a direction normal to the surface): 95 % of the acquired intensity comes from a depth up to 1.195 μm, and 99 % of the acquired intensity comes from a depth up to 1.836 μm. The Bruker DIFFRAC.EVA with the database of diffraction standards ICDD PDF4+ 2022 [52] and DIFFRAC.TOPAS programs were used for phase analysis and to refine the models of the identified phases to satisfactorily describe the experimental diffraction patterns. The TOPAS program uses the fundamental parameters profile fitting (FPPF) approach to account for instrumental effects and the Rietveld approach to optimize the model crystal structures' parameters (lattice constants, size- and strain broadening effect - following double-Voigt function approach [53], sites occupancies, background profile). Diffraction peak intensities are calculated based on structure factor and can be altered under the influence of DWF (Debye-Waller factor being the result of the original Debye-Waller theory of structure thermal disorder) and the modeled preferential orientation (PO) of the crystallites (but there was no need to include PO in the models). In the case of GID DPs, the instrumental contribution to the peak broadening was assessed based on the measurement of the reference material – LaB₆ NIST SRM 660b – using the same diffractometer geometry. The FWHM anisotropy of the BCC peaks has been observed in

Fig. 1. Damage profile (black line) and Fe ions range (red line) as a function of the sample depth calculated using SRIM software for Fe²⁺ irradiation (energy of 10 MeV): a) ODS-1-Ti irradiated with fluence of 1×10^{15} ions/cm² and b) ODS-2-TiV irradiated with fluence of 5×10^{15} ions/cm².

the DPs acquired for virgin areas using the BB geometry, i.e., the FWHM of the consecutive peaks is not increasing proportionally to a combined $(\cos\theta)^{-1} \cdot (\tan\theta)^{-1}$ function. The FWHM anisotropy has been associated with the anisotropy of local lattice strains and has been accounted for by incorporating the phenomenological model by Stephens [54]. As further described by, e.g., Leineweber [55], the refined S400 and S220 model parameters (only these 2 apply for the cubic systems) can be related to the variance (i.e., the average squared difference between the given value of the variable and its expected value) of microstrain $\langle(\Delta\epsilon_{hkl})^2\rangle$.

The Vickers microhardness measurements were performed under a load of 4.90 N using a DuraVision G5 device by ZwickRoell. The specimens for microhardness measurements were hot mounted and then gently mechanically polished using SiC papers (P180-P2400). The final polishing was conducted using diamond suspensions with particle sizes of 3.0, 1.0, and 0.25 μm . Ten measurements per sample were conducted to ensure reliable results. Tensile tests were performed using miniaturized specimens to characterize the mechanical properties of prepared alloys in as-sintered conditions and after annealing at 475 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. The size of miniaturized specimens (thickness of 0.62 mm and width of 0.80 mm) and the sketch of how the specimens were cut from the sintered materials are shown in Fig. 2. The tensile tests were performed at room temperature and at high temperatures up to 800 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ using a ZwickRoell Allround Z020 testing machine. The tests were performed at the strain rate of 10^{-3} s^{-1} . The strain was measured using a laser-based digital image correlation (DIC) system. At least three specimens were tested for each condition. The heating was performed at the rate of 20 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$, and the specimens were held at testing temperature for 5 minutes to ensure a homogeneous temperature distribution. The nanoindentation experiments were conducted using a NanoTest Vantage System by Micro Materials Ltd. to evaluate the hardening caused by ion implantation. Loads of indentation were selected to assess the ion-irradiated layers [49]. All measurements were performed at room temperature using a Berkovich-shaped diamond indenter tip. Dwell time was fixed at 2 s for all loads. Loading and unloading times were fixed according to loads: for lower loads, i.e., 0.5–4 mN (5 s loading and 3 s unloading), and for

higher loads, i.e., 5–15 mN (10 s and 5 s). For each load, 20 indents were performed with a 20 μm spacing between them. The nanoindentation data was analyzed using Oliver and Pharr method [56].

3. Results

3.1. Microstructure and mechanical properties

Microstructural observations reveal a ferritic matrix and many oxide and carbide precipitates in both studied alloys. The average grain size of bcc grains in both studied samples is relatively similar, i.e., for ODS-1-Ti alloy is 540 nm, while for ODS-2-TiV alloy is 600 nm. However, the volume fraction of nanometric precipitates is higher in the sample containing vanadium (2.64 %) compared to the vanadium-free sample (2.02 %). Although the average size of precipitates in both samples is between 10 and 50 nm, the slightly smaller precipitate size is found in the vanadium-containing sample (26 nm in ODS-1-Ti vs. 24 nm in ODS-2-TiV). Therefore, the vanadium addition leads to a higher number of precipitates, and their average size is smaller. Most oxide precipitates are aluminum-rich, which is common for FeCrAl ODS alloys [57]. More information on the microstructure of produced samples can be found in our previous paper [44].

Fig. 3. Tensile tests performed using miniaturized specimens reveal some differences in strength between the two compositions tested in the study. Representative engineering stress-strain curves are shown in Fig. 4, and the obtained values of parameters (yield strength, ultimate tensile strength, and plastic strain at failure) are summarized in Table 2. Both alloys reveal very high mechanical strength at room temperature; however, the alloy with vanadium (ODS-2-TiV) has higher strength than those without vanadium (ODS-1-Ti) at all testing temperatures. It highlights vanadium's positive impact on improving the FeCrAl- Y_2O_3 ODS strength. It is noticeable that the strength of both alloys decreases with increasing test temperature, but in general, alloys show good mechanical strength up to 600–650 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. The yield strength at 600 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ of ODS-1-Ti alloy is $490 \pm 8 \text{ MPa}$, while the yield strength at 600 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ of ODS-2-TiV alloy is $541 \pm 18 \text{ MPa}$. The total elongation is the highest in the 600–650 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ range, especially in the vanadium-containing samples. The total elongation at room temperature is above 10 %, which is a good result for powder metallurgy-produced ODS alloys. It is comparable to other investigated ODS alloys [11,31,58–61]; however, some authors obtained higher elongation [4,9]. It should be considered that the uncertainties of measurement of total elongation could be higher in the case of miniaturized samples than in standard specimens. Thus, at least three specimens per temperature were tested to obtain reliable results.

The fracture surface observations after the tensile tests at room temperature reveal both dimples and cleavage fracture regions in the fracture surface. Cleavage fracture is common in ODS alloys prepared by SPS techniques [61]. However, large areas of dimples, indicating ductile fracture, are present in the studied alloys. There are no significant differences between both studied alloys. The SEM images revealing dimples are shown in Fig. 5. The EBSD investigations show the deformation of grains after tensile tests at all tested temperatures alongside the direction of the application of the load. It confirms that plastic deformation occurs in all samples. The selected EBSD inverse pole figure orientation maps are shown in Fig. S2 (please refer to the Supplementary Materials).

3.2. Resistance to “475 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ embrittlement”

The annealing at 475 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 1000 h was performed to evaluate the susceptibility of investigated alloys to embrittlement at 475 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. The so-called “475 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ embrittlement” is often found in ferritic steels having high content chromium. It is related to the bcc matrix phase separation into Fe-rich (α phase) and Cr-rich (α' phase). The EBSD investigations, shown in Fig. 6., reveal small changes in the grain size of bcc phases during annealing. The grain size in the ODS-1-Ti alloy increases from

Fig. 2. Sketch showing how the tensile specimens were cut: a) cross-section of sintered sample from which miniaturized tensile specimens were cut, b) miniaturized tensile specimen dimensions.

Fig. 3. SEM-BSE images of microstructure of bulk samples after sintering: a) ODS-1-Ti, b) ODS-2-TiV.

Fig. 4. Selected engineering stress-strain curves acquired in tensile tests at room and high temperatures: a) ODS-1-Ti, b) ODS-2-TiV.

Table 2

Summary of the parameters measured in the tensile test: yield strength (YS), ultimate tensile strength, and total elongation.

Sample	Testing temperature [°C]	Yield strength [MPa]	Ultimate tensile strength [MPa]	Total elongation [%]
ODS-1-Ti	RT	769 ± 24	902 ± 6	13 ± 1
	300	689 ± 14	871 ± 14	11 ± 2
	500	608 ± 4	723 ± 16	13 ± 2
	600	490 ± 8	526 ± 14	17 ± 4
	650	366 ± 11	382 ± 18	21 ± 7
	700	263 ± 18	273 ± 21	21 ± 7
	800	165 ± 8	174 ± 11	17 ± 8
ODS-2-TiV	RT	893 ± 23	993 ± 10	12 ± 2
	300	856 ± 12	982 ± 11	9 ± 2
	500	783 ± 9	853 ± 10	14 ± 3
	600	541 ± 18	569 ± 13	25 ± 8
	650	392 ± 19	415 ± 19	32 ± 8
	700	282 ± 11	295 ± 17	21 ± 9
	800	176 ± 9	190 ± 12	18 ± 9

540 nm in the as-sintered state to 680 nm after annealing at 475 °C for 1000 h. The grain size in the ODS-2-TiV alloys is stable, i.e., 600 nm in as-sintered conditions vs. 610 nm after annealing. The histograms of grain size (Figs. 6b and 6c) show only very minor changes in the grain size distribution of the matrix phase. The orientation of grains is random in both alloys, which is usual for samples prepared using the SPS technique.

The hardness after the annealing at 475 °C for 1000 h increases slightly in both tested samples (Table 3). The increase is somewhat more pronounced in the ODS-1-Ti sample (4.5 %) than in the ODS-2-TiV

sample (2.8 %). It suggests that the annealing causes more significant microstructural changes in the sample without vanadium. However, the increase in both cases is quite limited compared to the literature results, e.g., a 50 % hardness increase of hardness after annealing at 475 °C for 1000 h was obtained by Capdevila et al. in another ODS alloy [32].

The tensile test results obtained at room temperature reveal significantly different behavior of both samples after 475 °C annealing, mainly in terms of total elongation. Total elongation decreases considerably in the ODS-1-Ti alloy from 13 ± 1 % as-sintered to 4 ± 1 % after annealing. In contrast, in the ODS-2-TiV alloy, there is almost no significant change in the plastic strain at failure (12 ± 2 % as-sintered and 11 ± 3 % after annealing). Therefore, the results show that the addition of vanadium significantly increases the resistance to “475 °C embrittlement”. The yield strength is somewhat similar in both ODS-1-Ti samples, i.e., 769 ± 24 MPa in as-sintered and 759 ± 10 MPa after the annealing. Despite the hardness increase after the annealing, the ultimate tensile strength is slightly higher in the as-sintered state (902 ± 6 MPa) than after the annealing (878 ± 9 MPa). It could be related to the brittleness of the alloy after the annealing at 475 °C, which fractures before achieving higher strength. In the case of the ODS-2-TiV alloy, both yield strength (893 ± 23 MPa vs. 928 ± 15 MPa) and ultimate tensile strength (993 ± 10 MPa vs. 1019 ± 5 MPa) increase slightly after the annealing at 475 °C for 1000 h. The SEM images of the fracture surface after tensile tests of samples after the annealing at 475 °C for 1000 h, shown in Fig. S3 (please refer to the Supplementary Materials), indicate that the majority of fracture surface regions reveal intergranular brittle fracture; however, some regions show ductile fracture character.

Fig. 7. The TEM investigations were performed to evaluate microstructural changes during the annealing at 475 °C for 1000 h at a finer

Fig. 5. SEM-SE electron images of fracture surface after tensile test at room temperature: a) overall image of ODS-1-Ti, b) high magnification image of ODS-1-Ti, c) overall image of ODS-2-TiV, d) high magnification image of ODS-2-TiV.

Fig. 6. EBSD results of ODS-1-Ti and ODS-2-TiV alloys in an as-sintered state and after 475 °C annealing for 1000 h: a) EBSD inverse pole figure maps, b) histogram of bcc phase grain size of the ODS-1-Ti alloy, c) histogram of bcc phase grain size of the ODS-2-TiV alloy.

Table 3

The hardness of the samples in as-sintered conditions and after 475 °C annealing for 1000 h.

Sample	Hardness [HV0.5]	
	as-sintered	after 475 °C annealing for 1000 h
ODS-1-Ti	330 ± 9	345 ± 3
ODS-2-TiV	353 ± 6	363 ± 8

scale. The TEM images of nanometric precipitates and histograms demonstrating their size distribution are shown in Fig. 8. The results reveal a slight volume fraction increase of nanometric oxide precipitates after 475 °C annealing, i.e., from 2.02 % to 2.21 % in ODS-1-Ti alloy and from 2.64 % to 2.80 % in ODS-2-TiV alloy. It is probably the effect of the formation of additional oxide precipitates during annealing instead of the growth of existing ones. The histograms of the precipitate size distribution (Figs. 8c and d) show a significantly higher volume fraction of the smallest precipitates (diameter below 15 nm) after annealing at 475 °C in both studied samples. It confirms that these precipitates nucleate

Fig. 7. Engineering strain-stress curves acquired in tensile tests at room temperature in as-sintered and after annealing at 475 °C for 1000 h samples: a) ODS-1-Ti, b) ODS-2-TiV.

and grow during annealing for 1000 h. The chromium local micro- or nano-segregation, usually responsible for 475 °C embrittlement, was not found using STEM-EDS mapping. The potential chromium segregation (the formation of α' phase) that causes the brittleness of the ODS-1-Ti sample could be too small (below the STEM-EDS resolution limit) to be detected. Therefore, the authors plan to perform atom probe tomography (APT) investigations in future studies. However, the increase in brittleness could also be potentially related to the rise in the oxide precipitate volume fraction.

3.3. Resistance to ion irradiation

The ion-implantations (Fe^{2+}) were performed to evaluate the irradiation resistance of investigated FeCrAl ODS alloys. The ODS-1-Ti sample was ion-irradiated up to 1 dpa, while the ODS-2-TiV sample was ion-irradiated up to 5 dpa. The XRD investigations were performed to evaluate irradiation-induced changes in structural parameters. The acquired XRD patterns (shown in Fig. 9) reveal a single bcc phase structure (space group: $I m\bar{3}m$) in pristine and ion-irradiated areas. The presence of nanometric oxides is not detected by XRD investigations due to their small size and relatively low volume fraction. It is consistent with our previous publications on these alloys [7,44]. The structural parameters calculated from XRD investigations are shown in Table 4. The determined microstrain parameter (ϵ_0) is defined as average local deviations of the interplanar distance d , i.e., $\epsilon_0 = \Delta d/d$, and reflects the density of defects (mainly point ones) in the layer close to the sample surface. After the total implantation dose of 1 dpa has been reached, the microstrain parameter increases by 67 % compared to the initial value in the ODS-1-Ti alloy, while ϵ_0 increases by 345 % in the case of a 5 dpa dose in the ODS-2-TiV alloy. The results show a decrease of unit cell constant (a_{bcc}) after ion implantation. This decrease corresponds well with the increase in the defect density and may be interpreted as the formation of voids or vacancies that make the structure shrink. Further inspection of a_{bcc} shows that the V-containing sample (ODS-2-TiV) has a bigger a_{bcc} by 0.03–0.04 pm ($3\text{--}4 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ \AA}$) in contrast to the fact that Fe (lower concentration in ODS-2-TiV than in ODS-1-Ti) is the biggest and heaviest atom among the others.

The nanoindentation measurements were performed to evaluate ion irradiation-induced hardening. The hardness results as a function of depth are shown in Fig. 10. The hardness results of virgin samples from nanoindentation are in good agreement with the microhardness measurements shown in Table 3. The hardness of the vanadium-containing sample (ODS-2-TiV) is higher than the vanadium-free sample (ODS-1-

Ti), which again highlights the positive impact of the vanadium addition on hardness. Both tested alloys reveal an increase of hardness after ion irradiation, which is the most commonly observed behavior of irradiated metallic materials [6,62]. The hardness increase between virgin and ion-irradiated samples is demonstrated in Fig. 11. Although the rise of the microstrain parameter is more pronounced in ODS-2-TiV alloy after ion irradiation to 5 dpa (Table 4), the increase of hardness after ion irradiation is similar in both tested samples. The hardness increases by 0.38 GPa in the ODS-1-Ti alloy irradiated to 1 dpa and by 0.34 GPa in the ODS-2-TiV alloy irradiated to 5 dpa.

The TEM investigations were carried out to evaluate the microstructural changes induced by ion irradiation. The TEM chemical composition analyses do not show significant changes, highlighting a lack of phase separation. The investigation focused on the evolution of nanometric oxide precipitates and irradiation-induced defects. The TEM results show that the volume fraction of nanometric oxide precipitates is similar in pristine alloys and after ion-irradiation, i.e., for ODS-1-Ti, the volume fraction in the peak damage zone after irradiation up to 1 dpa is 1.99 % vs. 2.02 % in the pristine state and for ODS-2-TiV, the volume fraction in the peak damage zone after irradiation up to 5 dpa is 2.66 % vs. 2.64 % in the pristine state. The TEM images before and after irradiation are shown in Fig. 12. The histograms of the size distribution of nanometric precipitates (Figs. 12c and 12f) do not reveal significant changes in the size of precipitates. Therefore, the precipitates are stable after conducting ion irradiations.

The TEM investigations of the dislocation structure in pristine and irradiated regions of ODS-1-Ti and ODS-2-TiV samples show an increase of dislocation density after ion irradiation. The TEM images are shown in Fig. 13. The increase of dislocation density after irradiation can be clearly seen in the TEM images under two-beam conditions. Such behavior is typical for alloys operating under irradiation conditions [42]. The dislocation density increases from $2.68 \times 10^{14} \pm 0.2 \times 10^{14} \text{ m}^{-2}$ in the pristine state to $4.01 \times 10^{14} \pm 0.4 \times 10^{14} \text{ m}^{-2}$ after ion-irradiation of ODS-1-Ti to 1 dpa and from $3.10 \times 10^{14} \pm 0.6 \times 10^{14} \text{ m}^{-2}$ in the pristine state to $5.16 \times 10^{14} \pm 0.4 \times 10^{14} \text{ m}^{-2}$ after ion-irradiation of ODS-2-TiV to 5 dpa. The dislocation density is relatively high in pristine samples; however, these values are common in the samples prepared by the powder metallurgy route [6,9,63]. The black dots visible on TEM images of pristine samples (Figs. 13a and 13c) are defect clusters. It should be noted that in the samples produced by powder metallurgy techniques in non-irradiated conditions, dislocation density varies significantly between the grains [31]. No voids after irradiation are present in both samples, which is consistent with other

Fig. 8. TEM results of samples after annealing at 475 °C: a) over-focused TEM bright field image showing precipitates in ODS-1-Ti alloy, b) over-focused TEM bright field image showing precipitates in ODS-2-TiV alloy, c) histogram of the size distribution of nanometric (<100 nm) precipitates in ODS-1-Ti alloy in as-sintered state and after 475 °C annealing, d) histogram of the size distribution of nanometric (<100 nm) precipitates in ODS-2-TiV alloy in as-sintered state and after annealing at 475 °C.

studies on FeCrAl alloys [64].

4. Discussion

4.1. Mechanical properties

To better understand the mechanical properties of the studied FeCrAl-Y₂O₃ ODS alloys at room temperature, we perform calculations of various strengthening mechanisms. Depending on the structure and microstructure, the contributions of the strengthening mechanism can be significantly different. In ODS alloys, we can name five primary sources of strengthening: Peierls-Nabarro stress (σ_0), solid-solution strengthening (σ_{ss}), grain boundary strengthening (σ_{GB}), dislocation strengthening (σ_p), dispersion strengthening (σ_{dis}). The expected yield strength (σ_y) could be calculated using the following formula [9,11,12,15,65,66]:

$$\sigma_y = \sigma_0 + \sigma_{ss} + \sigma_{GB} + \sqrt{\sigma_p^2 + \sigma_{dis}^2} \quad (1)$$

The stress needed to move a dislocation in a perfect lattice (lattice

resistance) is called the Peierls-Nabarro stress and can be calculated using the following formula [65]:

$$\sigma_0 = \frac{2M\mu}{1-\nu} \exp\left(\frac{-2\pi a}{b(1-\nu)}\right) \quad (2)$$

where: ν is the Poisson's ratio; b represents the size of the Burgers vector; a is the lattice parameter of the matrix phase; μ is the shear modulus of the matrix phase; and M is the Taylor factor. The ν is equal to 0.33, which is typical for metallic materials. The size of the Burgers vector for the matrix is 0.248 nm [67], and the shear modulus is 81,600 MPa [67]. M is 3.07 [68], and a is 0.2885 nm based on XRD data. The Peierls-Nabarro, calculated according to Eq. (2), is approximately 14 MPa for both samples.

The solid solution strengthening of the Fe-based bcc matrix considers only the main elements in the matrix and could be calculated using Eq. (3) [69]. It is believed that the contribution from interstitial atoms (C, O) is negligible because the concentration of these elements is low in the solid solution since they are mainly in the precipitates (oxides and carbides).

Fig. 9. XRD results of ODS-1-Ti (a) and ODS-2-TiV (b) samples. Black curves represent the XRD pattern acquired in the Bragg-Brentano para-focusing geometry from the virgin area of each sample, while blue curves represent the XRD pattern acquired using grazing incidence XRD from an ion-implanted area.

Table 4

Bcc phase structural parameters based on conducted XRD investigations: $a_{\text{bcc}} \equiv$ unit cell constant; $\varepsilon_o \equiv$ microstrain parameter. The last figure of regression error is given in parentheses.

Sample	a_{bcc} [Å]	ε_o
ODS-1-Ti-virgin	2.8850 (1)	0.00018 (1)
ODS-1-Ti-1dpa	2.8846 (1)	0.00030 (2)
ODS-2-TiV-virgin	2.8853 (1)	0.00020 (1)
ODS-2-TiV-5dpa	2.8850 (1)	0.00089 (2)

$$\sigma_{ss} = 0.00689 \sum k_i X_i^n \quad (3)$$

where: k_i is the strengthening coefficient of an alloying element; and X_i is the atomic concentration of a given element in the solid solution. Based on the literature [69,70], $k_{Cr} = 1400$, $k_{Al} = 4000$, $k_{Ti} = 4000$, $k_V = 4000$. The calculated σ_{ss} for ODS-1-Ti is 216 MPa, and for ODS-2-TiV is 235 MPa.

The grain boundary strengthening in samples with grain size larger than 100 nm could be determined using the following Hall-Petch equation [71]:

$$\sigma_{GB} = \frac{k_{HP}}{\sqrt{D}} \quad (4)$$

where: k_{HP} is the Hall-Petch coefficient, and D is the average grain size. Based on the literature, the k_{HP} is fixed at $150 \text{ MPa } \mu\text{m}^{1/2}$ since it is believed that the interstitial atoms that could increase this coefficient are mainly in precipitates [72]. The measured grain size is 540 nm and 600 nm for ODS-1-Ti and ODS-2-TiV, respectively. The calculated σ_{GB} is 204 MPa for ODS-1-Ti and 194 MPa for ODS-2-TiV.

The dislocation strengthening due to dislocations present in the material before deformation could be calculated using the following equation [73]:

$$\sigma_\rho = M\alpha\mu b\rho^{1/2} \quad (5)$$

where: ρ is the dislocation density; and α is the enhancement coefficient. Based on the measurements, the dislocation density is $2.68 \times 10^{14} \text{ m}^{-2}$ in ODS-1-Ti and $3.10 \times 10^{14} \text{ m}^{-2}$ in ODS-2-TiV. The α is 0.33 based on the literature [74]. The calculated σ_ρ is 335 MPa for ODS-1-Ti and 360 MPa for ODS-2-TiV.

The dispersion strengthening due to the presence of nanometric

Fig. 10. Nanoindentation results (hardness vs. contact depth) of samples in virgin state and after ion irradiation at 300 °C: a) ODS-1-Ti and b) ODS-2-TiV.

Fig. 11. The hardness of ODS-1-Ti and ODS-2-TiV samples in virgin state and after ion irradiation.

oxide precipitates could be calculated using the following formula [67]:

$$\sigma_{dis} = \frac{0.176M\mu b f^{1/2}}{d} \ln \frac{d}{2b} \quad (6)$$

where: f is the volume fraction of precipitates and d is their average diameter. The volume fraction of precipitates is 2.02 % and 2.64 % for ODS-1-Ti and ODS-2-TiV alloys, respectively. The mean size of the precipitate is 26 nm and 24 nm for ODS-1-Ti and ODS-2-TiV, respectively. The precipitate size is relatively large; however, in other ODS

with Al, the precipitates are pretty large too [8,75]. The calculated σ_{dis} is 236 MPa for ODS-1-Ti and 286 MPa for ODS-2-TiV.

The summary of the calculations of different strengthening contributions and the comparison of theoretical and experimentally measured yield strength are shown in Table 5. The calculations for ODS-2-TiV are in perfect agreement with the experimental results. For ODS-1-Ti alloy, the measured yield strength is lower than the predicted by calculations. It can be the result of multiple factors. There is a significant scattering of the grain size; there are many very small below 500 nm and large grains of a few micrometers. The dislocation density was calculated in a relatively small area, which cannot entirely represent the whole sample. Moreover, there are some approximations in the calculations, e.g., for solid solution strengthening, all alloying elements are considered to be present in the bcc matrix, while in reality, some fraction of these elements are in nanometric oxide and carbide precipitates. Based on the literature search, it was found that theoretical calculations are in good agreement for many ODS alloys [4,11]; however, sometimes, the calculated yield strength could be higher than the measured one [3,9].

Comparing the mechanical strength to other ODS alloys, the investigated alloys reveal high strength both at room and high temperatures, e.g., the studied alloys present higher strength at room temperature and 700 °C than Fe-5Cr-4.5Al-0.6Zr ODS studied by Cao and Zhou [12]. The comparison of yield strength and ultimate tensile strength of the investigated alloys with other ODS alloys studied in the literature is shown in Fig. 14. The investigated alloys present the fine grain size of the bcc matrix phase between 540 and 600 nm, which is smaller than in many other studied ODS alloys. It has a positive impact on mechanical properties. Yang et al. [3], in their studies on FeCrAl ODS alloys with the addition of Zr and Ti, obtained matrix grains between 1 and 2 μ m. Moreover, the nanometric precipitate volume fraction is significantly higher than in different studies on ODS alloys. Yang et al. [3] measured the volume fraction of precipitates between 0.37 and 0.49 % in FeCrAl

Fig. 12. TEM results concerning precipitates evolution during ion irradiation: a) TEM image of the pristine area in ODS-1-Ti, b) TEM image in the peak damage area in ODS-1-Ti, c) histogram of the size distribution of precipitates in ODS-1-Ti, d) TEM image of the pristine area in ODS-2-TiV, e) TEM image in the peak damage area in ODS-2-TiV, f) histogram of the size distribution of precipitates in ODS-2-TiV.

Fig. 13. TEM bright field images taken under two-beam conditions using diffraction vectors indicated on the images: a) pristine area in ODS-1-Ti, b) irradiated peak area in ODS-1-Ti, c) pristine area in ODS-2-TiV, d) irradiated peak area in ODS-2-TiV.

Table 5

Summary of the calculation of different strengthening mechanisms' contribution to the yield strength.

Strengthening mechanism	FeCrAl-Y ₂ O ₃ ODS sample	
	ODS-1-Ti	ODS-2-TiV
σ_0	14 MPa	14 MPa
σ_{ss}	216 MPa	235 MPa
σ_{GB}	204 MPa	194 MPa
σ_p	335 MPa	360 MPa
σ_{dis}	236 MPa	286 MPa
Total calculated contributions (theoretical σ_y)	844 MPa	903 MPa
Measured yield strength (σ_y)	769 MPa	893 MPa

ODS alloys with the addition of Ti and Zr, which is significantly lower than >2 % in the studied alloys. However, most oxides are aluminum-rich, which are usually larger than titanium-rich or zirconium-rich [4,60,76]. A higher strength of the alloy with vanadium is mainly the result of a higher volume fraction of precipitates. Other authors found beneficial effects of vanadium addition on the properties of ODS alloys. Woong Park et al. [19] also found that the addition of vanadium increases the hardness due to solid solution strengthening and limits grain growth during sintering and long-term operation at high temperatures. ODS-2-TiV alloy present higher strength and comparable elongation to 14Cr-2W-0.3Ti-0.3Y₂O₃ ODS [31], 16Cr-0.6Zr ODS [11], 16Cr3Al-0.5Zr ODS [77] or 14Cr-Zr-ODS [60] alloys consolidated by HIP. It is pretty remarkable since HIPed samples present near full

density. Another effect observed throughout many studies is that FeCrAl-ODS materials produced using powder metallurgy techniques tend to exhibit relatively poor ductility. This behavior of ODS alloys is also confirmed during the present study. Smaller total elongation of investigated alloys than in some other ODS alloys prepared by powder metallurgy could be related to rather large oxide precipitates. Due to the relatively high content of aluminum and lower content of other oxide-forming elements, as most observed oxides are aluminum-rich, which tends to form bigger than titanium or zirconium-rich precipitates. Yan et al. [4] found that smaller average oxide particle size positively impacts the elongation of FeCrAl ODS. The elongation is the most significant at 600–650 °C, then decreases. It is in agreement with other studies showing that in these temperatures, the plastic deformation in FeCrAl ODS tends to have a viscoplastic character, desirable in materials operating under extreme thermomechanical conditions. In contrast, at higher temperatures in α -Fe based alloys, damage develops rapidly, and fracture occurs with minimum tertiary creep [31].

4.2. Resistance to “475 °C embrittlement”

The investigated FeCrAl-Y₂O₃ ODS alloys show different behavior in the tensile test regarding total elongation. The vanadium-containing alloy shows no change in elongation after the 475 °C annealing for 1000 h. It again confirms that vanadium positively impacts the evolution of properties after the annealing. However, it should be noted that there is only a minimal increase of hardness after annealing in both samples, which suggests that the formation of the α' phase does not form

Fig. 14. Comparison of yield strength and ultimate tensile strength at various temperatures of the investigated alloys and ODS alloys studied in the literature.

or precipitate in limited amounts in the nano- or sub-nano areas as discussed earlier and demonstrated in Fig. 8. Similar minor hardness variations were found in studies of Fe13Cr5.5Al alloy by Hoffman et al. [78], and the authors also did not notice precipitation of α' phase. FeCrAl alloys with chromium content between 10 and 12 wt. % are usually not prone to 475 °C embrittlement [35]. However, Han et al. [36] found α' phase in the Fe-12Cr-5Al ODS, and hardness increased by approximately 30 HV after aging at 475 °C for 700 h. Higher chromium content, strictly 20 wt. % in the study by Capdevila et al. [32], promotes α - α' separation, and the authors confirmed approximately 50 % hardness increase after annealing at 475 °C for 1000 h. The content of Al also significantly impacts α' phase formation, as the addition of Al to Fe-Cr alloys could limit the susceptibility to 475 °C embrittlement [78]. It seems that the studied ODS-1-Ti alloy could be at the early stage of the formation of α' phase. TEM studies could not unambiguously observe the significant differences in microstructure to explain different behavior in tensile tests. It is well known that the limited resolution of TEM could prevent the observation of the nanometric α' phase [78]. Therefore, atom probe tomography (APT) investigations should be performed to analyze the potential formation of the α' phase in the future [32]. It should also be noted that the volume fraction of nanometric precipitates increases slightly during annealing, possibly contributing to the hardness increase. The volume fraction of the smallest precipitates increases, which suggests the nucleation of precipitates during annealing. The better resistance of ODS alloys to 475 °C embrittlement than those without nanometric oxide particles and complex precipitates is caused mainly by precipitates that affect Cr diffusion pathways [36,79,80]. Chen et al. [80] investigated SUS430 ferritic steel and 12Cr-ODS steel in terms of the resistance to 475 °C embrittlement caused by annealing up to 10,000 h. The authors found that SUS430 ferritic steel presents significant age-hardening, while 12Cr-ODS steel shows almost no hardening. Nanometric oxides act as trap sites for point defects and therefore decrease diffusion rate. It retards the formation of the α' phase. Thus, the higher volume fraction of precipitates in ODS-2-TiV could be the key factor in improving embrittlement resistance compared to ODS-1-Ti.

4.3. Irradiation resistance

The irradiation causes a hardness increase by 0.38 GPa in ODS-1-Ti (1 dpa) and by 0.34 GPa in ODS-2-TiV (5 dpa). Therefore, the hardness increase is similar in both samples in the margin of error. Nevertheless, the ODS-2-TiV sample was irradiated to the higher damage dose; thus, it should show higher hardening. On the other hand, it is well

known that the most important hardening effect occurs in low-damage doses, and further increasing of dpa results only in a slight hardness increase [6]. It seems that overall better resistance to irradiation-induced hardening of ODS-2-TiV than ODS-1-Ti alloy could be the effect of a higher volume fraction of nanometric precipitates in ODS-2-TiV (volume fraction of precipitates of 2.64 %) than in ODS-1-Ti (volume fraction of precipitates of 2.02 %). For more details related to the nanometric precipitates in virgin samples, please refer to our previous publications [7,44]. The nanometric precipitates could act as sinks for irradiation-induced defects, mitigating radiation damage. It is confirmed by the fact that the increase of dislocation density after ion irradiation is lower in ODS-2-TiV than in ODS-1-Ti alloy. Furthermore, the ion irradiation-induced hardness increase is lower in investigated samples (<10 %) than in the studies by Kondo et al. [38], where the hardness increase in Fe-12Cr-6Al-0.4Zr-0.5Ti-0.5Y₂O₃ ODS alloy irradiated by Fe⁺ ions to 5 dpa is approximately 20 % compared to the pristine sample. The hardness increase of the studied ODS alloys is also significantly lower than that of Fe-12.5Cr-4.5Al-4Mo without oxide particles studied by Li et al. [64]. The authors found the hardness increases after Fe²⁺ ions irradiation by almost 42 % at 1 dpa and by approximately 59 % at 5 dpa. In some cases, the irradiation of ODS alloy could result in a hardness decrease or limited hardening due to the dissolution of nanometric precipitates under irradiation [39]. However, the precipitate volume fraction is similar in the studied samples after irradiation to the pristine sample.

Another essential effect closely related to the irradiation resistance of the FeCrAl-Y₂O₃ ODS alloy is that nanometric complex oxide precipitates can change significantly under such conditions, further impacting mechanical properties [39,42]. Some investigations report that oxide nanoprecipitates can dissolve under irradiation due to the ejection of atoms [41]. Other investigations show the growth of precipitates during irradiation due to the creation of vacancies that can facilitate the diffusion of elements from the matrix phase to oxide [39], while other researchers demonstrate almost no change in the size of oxide precipitates [40]. Moreover, studies by Ribis et al. [41] showed that irradiation temperature significantly affects the evolution of nanoprecipitates. At room temperature irradiation, the precipitates' size decreases, and precipitates dissolve. After irradiation at medium temperature, usually between 300 and 500 °C, the precipitates seem stable because the effect of ballistic ejection, responsible for their dissolution, and thermal diffusion, responsible for the coarsening of precipitates, compensate each other. At high temperatures, thermal diffusion is more pronounced, and leading to coarsening of precipitates. Nevertheless, Santra et al. [81] found a decrease of oxide precipitate size under

irradiation at 700 °C. In the studied FeCrAl-Y₂O₃ ODS alloys, the volume fraction and size of oxide precipitates do not change at least for irradiation up to 5 dpa. It shows a good stability of produced oxide particles. A similar stability of oxide precipitates was found in the study by Kondo et al. [38]. However, it should be noted that many studies analyzing the significant evolution of precipitates were conducted for higher irradiation doses, even up to 100 dpa [39].

5. Conclusions

The conducted investigations demonstrate very promising properties of FeCrAl ODS alloys with the additions of Y₂O₃, Ti, and V for applications in Generation IV nuclear reactors. Moreover, the results highlight the impact of the minor alloying addition of vanadium in tuning the properties of ODS alloys. Both tested alloys present good mechanical properties, mainly due to the combination of various strengthening mechanisms such as dispersion strengthening (nanometric precipitates) and grain boundary strengthening (fine grains with diameter below 1 μm). The addition of vanadium also causes an increase of the strength of the alloy at temperatures up to 800 °C while the ductility is somewhat similar to the vanadium-free material. The increase of strength is mainly the effect of a higher volume fraction of nanometric precipitates in the sample with vanadium. The addition of vanadium is also beneficial in preventing 475 °C embrittlement. The sample with vanadium presents similar ductility in the tensile test before and after the annealing at 475 °C for 1000 h. However, both tested samples reveal limited hardening after exposure at 475 °C and α' phase was not observed during the microstructure characterization campaign. Further atom probe tomography (APT) investigations are planned finally to confirm or deny the formation of the α' phase at nano and sub-nano areas. Both studied FeCrAl ODS alloys show promising irradiation resistance manifesting by limited hardening and the stability of nanometric precipitates after ion implantation up to 5 dpa at 300 °C. Moreover, the vanadium addition increases the irradiation resistance of produced FeCrAl ODS alloys. It is due to a higher volume fraction of precipitates, which act as sinks for defects mitigating irradiation-induced damage.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

T. Stasiak: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis. **J.J. Jasiński:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **M. Zieliński:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation, Formal analysis. **M. Wilczopolska:** Investigation. **A. Kosińska:** Investigation. **W. Chmurzyński:** Investigation. **K. Mulewska:** Investigation, Formal analysis. **R. Diduszko:** Investigation, Formal analysis. **M. Chmielewski:** Investigation, Formal analysis. **M. Kowal:** Investigation. **J. Rzempotuch:** Investigation. **K. Ciporska:** Investigation. **Ł. Kurpaska:** Supervision, Project administration, Funding acquisition. **J. Jagielski:** Supervision, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgment

SafetyG project - Safety of GFR through innovative materials, technologies and processes / Ensuring safe operation of a GFR reactor through the use of advanced materials, technologies and processes. Project implemented under Horizon 2020 Euratom (H2020-Euratom) No 945041 (project budget - EUR 249,469.00) and supported by the Ministry of Science and Higher Education with the amount of PLN 377,403.00 - contract No 5168/H2020-Euratom/2021/2 dated

01.03.2022.

Activities financed within the framework of the undertaking of the Ministry of Education and Science entitled "Technical Description of the Research High-Temperature Gas Cooled Reactor (HTGR)" in the years 2021–2024.

Parts of this research were carried out at IBC at the Helmholtz-Zentrum Dresden Rossendorf e. V., a member of the Helmholtz Association, through the implementation of RADIATE proposal no 22003083-ST-1.1-RADIATE. We would like to thank Dr. S. Akhmadaliev for his assistance.

The authors J.J. Jasiński, M. Zieliński, M. Wilczopolska, A. Kosińska, K. Mulewska, R. Diduszko, Ł. Kurpaska, J. Jagielski acknowledge the support from the European Union Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under NOMATEN Teaming grant agreement no 857470 and from the European Regional Development Fund via the Foundation for Polish Science International Research Agenda Plus program grant no MAB PLUS/2018/8 which partially covered their salaries during preparation of this article.

The publication was created within the framework of the project of the Minister of Science and Higher Education "Support for the activities of Centres of Excellence established in Poland under Horizon 2020" under contract no MEiN/2023/DIR/3795.

Supplementary materials

Supplementary material associated with this article can be found, in the online version, at [doi:10.1016/j.jnucmat.2025.156131](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jnucmat.2025.156131).

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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